

RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS AND CAPACITY BUILDING OF TEACHER EDUCATORS

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Abstract

The present study aimed to find out the relationship between teacher effectiveness and capacity building of the teacher educators. The investigator adapted normative survey method for the present study. Stratified random sampling techniques has been followed for the selection of sample from the population. The size of each stratum of the study has been decided based on the principle of disproportionate stratified sample. The sample includes 260 teacher educators from west zone of North 24 Parganas at West Bengal. Teacher effectiveness scale standardized by Umme Kulsum (2011) was adapted to measure the teacher effectiveness of teacher educators and it includes five areas of teacher effectiveness such as, preparation and planning for teaching, classroom management, knowledge of subject matter, teacher's characteristics and interpersonal relations. Capacity building scale validated by Geerish Cholayil (2012) was adapted to measure the capacity building of teacher educators and it includes four dimensions of capacity building such as capacity to promote learning in the classroom, capacity for critical self-evaluation and development, capacity for the collaboration with and influence colleagues and capacity to acquire educational and social values. The study showed that all the dimensions of teacher effectiveness have significant correlation with all the dimensions of capacity building, which revealed that the capacity building will absolutely help to increase effectiveness of teaching.

Keywords: *teacher effectiveness- capacity building- teacher educators*

1. INTRODUCTION

At present the teaching became a challenging job for teachers. Teacher communities are facing issues in every level from primary school to higher education. Due to fast changing of society and peoples need our educational priority has changed in past decades especially in the 21st century. In our present education system in India policies have been made for deconstruction of the system, gave great suggestions as it can meet global perspective, policy makers already took action to apply Sustainable Development Goal and also to reach massively to all the students and to promote "Education for all" by 2030 message, trying to achieve it at optimum level. Globally it is proved that educational system is going or already reached towards "Student centric learning" for better understanding. Where, teacher plays a pivotal role as "Facilitator". We all are agreed that without facilitating education, without professionalism, without continuous teaching and self-evaluation it would be exist only in printed book like just a great phrase.

2. NEED AND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Teacher effectiveness focus on teachers subject mastery, maintain teacher characteristics and utilize skills for planning, preparing and managing their classroom and building good relationship with students in teachers training colleges which enhances students achievement. Teacher effectiveness is a common variable in the field of educational research. Thus, exploring various factors associated with teacher effectiveness is a topic worthy of further study in the field of education. Huge number of studies has been already done worldwide focus upon relational or variables influencing on teacher effectiveness. The studies conducted by Podolsky et al., (2019) ; Buela et al., (2015); Pachaiyappan et al., (2014); Omotayo, (2014); Tyagi, (2013) showed that *teacher experience* has a positive relationship with teacher effectiveness, but opposed by Sadeghi et al., (2021). Mastrokoulou, (2022) revealed that the key issues closely related to teacher effectiveness is teaching style, course organization, student engagement, and determination of progress. Filmer et al., (2022); Nemiño, (2022) showed that the *Student achievement, academic performance* is also has a significant relationship with teacher effectiveness. Rogers (2018) pointed out that instructional planning and applying professional knowledge, differentiated instructional strategies, variety of assessment strategies, positive learning classroom environment, communication with students and parents created impact on student achievement. Saleman (2019) reported that *teacher quality* was positively related to students' academic performance and determine the success, also had same perception of students.

Building of capacity is a part of teachers' professional development. College and university teachers have the opportunity to develop their capacity through capacity building programme, faculty development programme, workshop, programme for young social science teacher by ICSSR, orientation programme, refresher course, induction programme, publication etc. Both Indian and Foreign studies indicated that the capacity building is the very important variable and closely associated with the teacher effectiveness. The study conducted by Jepaketer et al. (2015) revealed that the teachers capacity building strategy and *student performance*, got positive relationship between it; capacity building positively correlated and enhanced *teachers attitude* and *student development*. Khatoon et al. (2015) showed that the capacity building of teachers is positively influenced by *student academic performance* . Sureshkumar (2017) put light on capacity factors, measures of recharging factors, professional potential factors and institutional mechanism factors, which were correlated; Mutunga et al. (2022) expressed that principals' capacity building for teachers positively influences the student's academic performance.

Based on the review of related studies the researcher came to know that only very fewer studies did by Indian scholar with the variable capacity building of teacher especially teacher educators and its relationship with teacher effectiveness, so the researchers choose this area as their research gap of the study.

3. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

The objective of the study is to find out the relationship between different dimensions of capacity building and different dimensions of teacher effectiveness of teacher educators.

Suitable null hypotheses have been formulated and tested the hypotheses with the statistical analysis 'Pearson's co-efficient of correlation'.

4. METHOD OF THE STUDY

The investigator adapted normative survey method for the present study. Nature of the research is ex-post facto study. Here the population of the study were all teacher educators working in teacher's training institutions in the state of West Bengal. From this population the investigator took a chunk of population called sample unit from the district of North 24 Parganas at West Bengal. Stratified random sampling techniques has been followed for the selection of sample from the population. The size of each stratum of the study has been decided based on the principle of disproportionate stratified sample. The sample includes 260 teacher educators from west zone of North 24 Parganas at West Bengal. Teacher effectiveness scale standardized by Umme Kulsum (2011) was adapted to measure the teacher effectiveness of teacher educators and it includes five areas of teacher effectiveness such as, preparation and planning for teaching, classroom management, knowledge of subject matter, teacher's characteristics and interpersonal relations. Capacity building scale validated by Geerish Choleyil (2012) was adapted to measure the capacity building of teacher educators and it includes four dimensions of capacity building such as capacity to promote learning in the classroom, capacity for critical self-evaluation and development, capacity for the collaboration with and influence colleagues and capacity to acquire educational and social values.

5. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The coefficient of correlation has been carried out to find out the relationship between different dimensions of capacity building and the different dimensions of teacher effectiveness of teacher educators. The result of the analysis is presented in Table-1.

Table-1
CORRELATIONAL BETWEEN CAPACITY BUILDING AND TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHER EDUCATORS

Teacher Effectiveness Capacity Building	Preparation and Planning for Teaching	Classroom Management	Knowledge of Subject Matter	Teacher Characteristics	Interpersonal Relations	Total score of Teacher Effectiveness
Capacity to promote learning in the classroom	.604**	.686**	.567**	.815**	.496**	.535**
Capacity for critical self-evaluation and development	.726**	.680**	.561**	.659**	.561**	.553**
Capacity for the collaboration with an influence colleagues	.593**	.427**	.592**	.480**	.352**	.499**

Capacity to acquire educational and social values	.685**	.587**	.639**	.551**	.446**	.492**
Total score of Capacity Building	.870**	.646**	.854**	.673**	.744**	.874**

Note:**0.01 level of significance

Relationship between Preparation and Planning for Teaching and all the Dimensions of Capacity Building

Table-1 shows the 'r' value of relationship between preparation and planning for teaching and all the dimensions of capacity building. It revealed that the preparation and planning for teaching has positive and high correlation with all the dimensions capacity building along with total capacity building of teacher educators.

Relationship between Classroom Management and all the Dimensions of Capacity Building

Table-1 shows the 'r' value of relationship between class room management and all the dimensions of capacity building. It revealed that the classroom management has positive and marked relationship with all the dimensions capacity building along with total capacity building of teacher educators.

Relationship between Knowledge and Subject Matter and all the Dimensions of Capacity Building

Table-1 shows the 'r' value of relationship between knowledge and subject matter and all the dimensions of capacity building. It revealed that the knowledge and subject matter has positive and high correlation with all the dimensions capacity building along with total capacity building of teacher educators.

Relationship between Teacher Characteristics and all the Dimensions of Capacity Building

Table-1 shows the 'r' value of relationship between teacher characteristics and all the dimensions of capacity building. It revealed that the teacher characteristics has positive and marked relationship with all the dimensions capacity building along with total capacity building of teacher educators.

Relationship between Interpersonal Relations and all the Dimensions of Capacity Building

Table-1 shows the 'r' value of relationship between interpersonal relation and all the dimensions of capacity building. It revealed that the interpersonal relations has positive and high correlation with all the dimensions capacity building along with total capacity building of teacher educators.

Relationship between the total teacher effectiveness and all the Dimensions of Capacity Building

Table-1 shows the 'r' value of relationship between total teacher effectiveness and all the dimensions of capacity building. It revealed that the total teacher effectiveness has positive and high correlation with all the dimensions capacity building along with total capacity building of teacher educators.

6. CONCLUSION

It is clear from the statistical result that all the dimensions of teacher effectiveness have significant correlation with all the dimensions of capacity building. Teaching strategies and methods might vary on the basis of effectiveness of teaching, but capacity building will absolutely help to increase effectiveness of teaching. Capacity building scores shows that the ease of teacher educators to grow in their profession and improve more towards professionalism. This will help teacher educators as well as pupil teachers. They will charge or boost up the pupil teachers in enhancing the academic achievement and how to become a humane teacher in future. Capacity building and teacher effectiveness both will help pupil teachers to deal and cope with the present challenges of education system and 21st century learners.

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